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SOFC In-Field Test of a Tool for Advanced Monitoring, Diagnostics and Lifetime Prognostics

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Abstract

Accurate state-of-health (SoH) monitoring is considered a key element in avoiding faulty operation of fuel cell stacks. Such faulty operation could relate to problems in the balance-of-plant, having a global effect on the stack performance, or to problems in the stack itself, where the effect could initially be very local. This research topic was addressed in the European project INSIGHT, with the final aim to demonstrate advanced SoH monitoring in a real environment by implementing newly developed hardware equipped with novel perturbation routines and data fitting routines in a μ -CHP system from SOLIDpower. The results of the test that followed, including validation of the routines and hardware as well as simulation of different kinds of faulty operation, are reported here.

1. Introduction

Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFCs) are attractive technology in the field of combined heat and power generation due to their high power-to-heat ratio. In order to compete with other CHP technologies, SOFCs must be durable, with high, predictable performance and low maintenance costs. Thus, knowing the conditions of the system, with accurate health analysis, life prediction, fault analysis, fault prediction and fault mitigation, are essential. This has led to interest in analyzing process signals that contain information about the system's state of health (SoH), existing or imminent faults by means of fault detection and isolation (FDI) and prediction of the remaining useful life (RUL).

An important aspect in FDI is the comparison of the system performance with one that could be expected under non-faulty conditions. This can be assessed in several ways. Firstly, the actual performance can be compared with the one that is calculated by modeling under non-faulty conditions. Preferably, dynamic, quantitative models based on first principles are used. A popular classifier that uses such model data is the so-called fault signature matrix (FSM) that results from fault-tree analysis (FTA) [1-2]. Secondly, classifiers based on data-driven approaches have been reported, including wavelet transform [3-5], hybrid principal component analysis [6], support vector machine (SVM) [7], random forests (RFs) [8], neural networks [9-14], supervised self-organizing maps [15], and deep-learning networks [16]. Knowledge-based expert systems combined with a Bayesian network as a reasoner have been reported as well [17]. Thirdly, approaches that combine a quantitative model with a support vector machine or random forests data-driven classifier have been reported, which appear to be more effective than purely model-driven methods or data-driven methods, in particular where it concerns weak or complex interdependencies between faults and resulting symptoms, which are nonlinear by nature [18-19, 8]. Similarly encouraging results have been reported by combining a dynamic model with a multi-layer SVM classifier that preferably is linked with Fault Inference Tree Analysis (FITA) [20].

Available literature on SOFC-oriented remaining useful life (RUL) prediction is still relatively scarce. Some authors report about using the stack voltage as RUL indicator [7, 21-22]. Thus, the predictions are only valid when the operating conditions don't change over time. In a publication from Dolenc et al., the area specific resistance of the stack as signal for RUL prediction, supported by a nonlinear stack model, is therefore considered to be more useful than just the stack voltage [23].

In this paper, Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS), including both sine wave and pseudo-random binary signal (PRBS) excitation and Total Harmonic Distortion Analysis (THDA) have been deployed for fault detection on an EnGen-2500 system from SOLIDpower, housing two SOFC stacks with a total nominal power output of 2.5 kWe. Both EIS and THDA rely on imposing an AC perturbation on the DC load that is applied during fuel cell operation. With regard to EIS, results from a parametric study on SOLIDpower short-stacks have been reported by Ouweltjes et al. [24], revealing the following contributions in the impedance spectra:

- Peak below 1 Hz: Typically small peak that appeared when pure oxygen at the air electrode side was replaced with air, and thus suggested to be related to oxygen adsorption/desorption process;
- Peak around 4 Hz: Typically large peak related to gas conversion;
- Peak around 30 Hz: Typically small peak related to both cathode and anode, most likely gas diffusion through the anode substrate and cathode bulk diffusion;
- Peak around 1 kHz: Typically large peak that vastly diminished with current increase, related to the anode charge transfer reaction.

Similar investigations were carried out by Caliandro et al. [25]; by comparing the Distribution of Relaxation Times (DRT) results with outcomes from dynamic numerical model calculations that include gas and solid phase transport coupled with charge transfer and chemical reactions it was possible to assign 6 peaks where, deviating from the parametric study by Ouweltjes et al. [24], the peak below 1 Hz was also found to be dependent on fuel mass transport, while an additional peak revealed above 5 kHz, with unknown origin. Finally, a peak was found in the DRT graphs between 100 and 500 Hz that was related to the fuel composition but also was thermally activated. Therefore, there is a suspicion that this peak is partially caused by incomplete deconvolution of the charge transfer peak appearing at higher frequency [25].

THDA relies on imposing one or several perturbation signals in order to detect nonlinearities that indicate faulty operation, which appear as harmonics when the frequency distribution of the signal is analysed. While first demonstrated on PEM fuel cells [26] and then further improved and commercialized by AVL List, it has recently also been applied to SOFC stacks by Malafronte et al. to detect limits for fuel utilization [27]. Other nonlinearities besides fuel starvation could in principle be detected as well; in a publication from Thomas et al. [28] it was shown that the technique could distinguish oxidant related nonlinearities, detectable at frequencies below 100 Hz, and fuel related nonlinearities, appearing below 15 Hz. So by imposing two perturbation frequencies at the same time, both nonlinearities could be accurately identified.

In the next sections, a description of the tests performed on the commercial SOFC system from SOLIDpower is given. This includes the manufacture and usage of a so-called Monitoring, Diagnostic and Lifetime Tool (MDLT), equipped with algorithms to drive the power converter housed in the fuel cell system, and algorithms to perform advanced signal processing and lifetime prediction. This work was carried out in the European project INSIGHT.

2. Experimental

2.1 Description of the fuel cell system

The system that was used for the tests is schematically depicted in Figure 1. It is centered around a two-stack fuel cell arrangement for anode-supported cells operated around 750 °C delivering 2.5 kWe in total, controlled by a DC/DC power converter. The oxidant is preheated ambient air. The fuel is natural gas that is partially converted to syngas by means of an external steam reforming catalyst. Remaining fuel at the fuel cell outlet is burnt in an afterburner.

Figure 1. Flow scheme of the commercial SOFC system from SOLIDpower, called EnGen-2500.

Based on an inventory made by the project consortium in an early phase of the project, taking into account the operational experience of the project partners as well as field experience with the system, the following faults were identified as those that would be the most detrimental for the system:

- Anode reoxidation due to fuel starvation
- Carbon deposition in the reformer and/or stack due to steam shortage
- Gas leakage due to the failure of sealants in the stack

The diagnostic routines developed in the project were concentrating on the above 3 faults, with the assumption that other, less prominent faults and combined faults could be added after completion of the project by following the same rationale. Developed routines were validated by means of tests on short stacks representative of the SOLIDpower full stacks at EPFL and CEA, on full stacks at VTT and CEA, and on full stacks housed in a commercial system at SOLIDpower [29]. The experimental results shown below report about this last test.

2.2 Description of the developed diagnostic routines

The developed probing algorithms are dealing with imposing a sinusoidal perturbation or a pseudo-random binary signal (PRBS), both aiming at scanning the stack response between 10 kHz and 0.1 Hz, and single frequency sinusoidal perturbation used for THDA. While impedance spectra constructed from sinusoidal perturbation rely on calculating the phase shift in the imposed signal by the probed system, PRBS perturbs the system with a broadband signal, where the impedance is computed not at a single frequency but at a continuum of frequencies of interest by means of a continuous wavelet transform. Compared with sinusoidal perturbation, PRBS allows for significantly shortening the probing time, which is attractive for on-line fault detection [30].

Based on the considered faults and the available impedance spectroscopy and THDA algorithms, the fault signature matrix (FSM) was constructed, considering relevant features extracted from both spectrum deconvolution by means of DRT and Equivalent Circuit Modelling (ECM) approaches. The constructed FSM states that fuel starvation will appear as an increased gas conversion peak appearing in the low frequency part in impedance spectra, while it would slightly shift towards lower frequency. In addition, a drop in stack voltage, increased voltage fluctuations, and changes in pressure drops and temperatures in the system are anticipated. A shortage in steam most likely first reveals in the reformer where, once carbon starts to deposit, changes in reformer temperature and pressure drop will occur. As long as the reformer is not fully blocked while carbon deposition takes place, the amount of fuel that leaves the reformer will be less than normal, while it will be more enriched with hydrogen due to the dehydrogenation reaction. Much like fuel starvation, steam shortage will cause an increase of the gas conversion impedance while it shifts to lower frequency. Sealant failure will likely be most detrimental when it happens prior to the stack (e.g. in the fuel manifold) or within the stack close to the inlet. Considering the fact that only the stack voltage is probed, it will likely be difficult to detect sealant failures that affect only one repeat element in an early phase. For more severe sealant leakages, the effects will be similar to those observed for fuel starvation.

2.3 Description of the developed hardware

In order to diagnose the SOFC system from SOLIDpower, the company Bitron developed the Monitoring, Diagnostics and Lifetime Tool (MDLT). Where possible, the MDLT is based on widely available hardware components. It includes a custom-made analog front-end

board for sampling the SOFC current and voltage, a BeagleBone Black for running the selected configuration, accepting user inputs, acquisition commanding and for data storage, and a Raspberry Pi for running diagnostic algorithms and for showing outputs, an ethernet switch to realise communication between the 3 boards and the graphical user interface, and a power supply unit. The usage of a double board (i.e. the BeagleBone Black and the Raspberry Pi) allows for increasing the rapidity of the data acquisition and treatment.

An impression of how the MDLT was mounted on the system is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. MDLT mounted on the EnGen-2500 system from SOLIDpower: top: MDLT; bottom left: location of the MDLT at the back of the SOFC EnGen-2500 system; bottom right: front side of the EnGen 2500 installed in its testing location

3. Results

3.1 Test evolution

The system was tested over a time period of almost 7000 hours, see Figure 3. Advanced diagnosis was carried out only on one of the two stacks housed in the system. During the first two months (phase A), basic functionality tests with the MDLT took place, using algorithms that were developed during the European project HEALTHCODE, dealing with diagnosing PEMFC systems, and thus not yet optimized for SOFC operation. This helped to check proper communication between the MDLT and the DC/DC converter, and remote operation of the MDLT. During the following 6 months (phase B), validation with the SOFC algorithms took place, allowing the project partners to test and, if necessary, improve their algorithms. This test period was interrupted by a periodic regular maintenance at the SOLIDpower facilities after 2800 h of operation. After 5200 h of operation one of the stacks -not the one that was probed- deteriorated. This also affected the operation point of the probed stack. It was then decided to replace the faulty stack in order to complete the tests in a controlled way. After 6100 h of operation, issues occurred with the MDLT device that were solved by replacing the MDLT device with a bug-free copy.

As the time that remained in the project was limited, the FDI routine was only validated for fuel starvation. But in principle it would have been fit for detecting the other considered faults as well, as well as predicting the remaining useful life (RUL). During the experiments, the fuel utilization was kept modest, considering the normal operating conditions of the system, but that guaranteed sufficient stability over the test period to validate the algorithms. This validation took place both at 1030 W stack power output and 570 W stack power output (note that this is the power output of the probed stack), where the fuel utilization was systematically varied between 60 and 72%, and where a boundary for faulty operation was artificially set at 70%.

Figure 3. Evolution of the total stack power and stack temperature during the test.

3.2 THDA results

The experiments with respect to total harmonic distortion were designed to test the impact of the perturbation frequencies (between 0.1 and 1.0 Hz) and perturbation amplitudes (between 1 and 5 A) at different fuel utilizations. In addition, measurements were carried out at steady state to understand the stability of the voltage signal without perturbation. The results from the steady-state measurements, depicted in Figure 4, a strong periodic component of approximately 0.1 Hz can be observed, where an additional distortion in the voltage perturbation is present. This is typically not seen for stacks operated in dedicated test benches. This fluctuations are therefore thought to be related to the system control, which will complicate analyses that rely on signal perturbation.

Figure 4. Voltage and current fluctuations in steady state at 61% fuel utilization

Figure 5 highlights some important findings from the THD analysis. From the graph on the left it can be observed that, apart from measurements that took place at 61% fuel utilization, the nonlinearity of the signal increases with increasing fuel utilization, while the detectability of the nonlinearity increases with perturbation amplitude. While this could be related to a better signal-to-noise ratio, it should also be realised that higher AC amplitude drives the system more towards the nonlinear region. And from the graph on the right side it can be seen that for the perturbation amplitude of 5 A, the best discrimination is obtained at the lowest perturbation frequencies.

Figure 5. THD signal as a function of perturbation amplitude and fuel utilization at a perturbation frequency of 0.1 Hz (left side), and THD signal as a function of perturbation frequency and fuel utilization at a perturbation amplitude of 5 A (right side), all at a stack power output of 1030 W at 19.7 A DC current.

3.3 Impedance spectroscopy results

As explained previously, impedance spectra were obtained both by sinusoidal perturbation and PRBS, using 1.5 A perturbation in both cases. Examples of the quality of the obtained spectra are shown in Figure 6, from which it can be seen that the spectra basically contain two features, i.e. one with a maximum around 6 kHz (left arc in the plots) that is likely related to the anode charge transfer reaction, and one with a maximum around 0.2 Hz (right arc in the plots) that is likely related to gas conversion. At low frequency, the spectra are noisy and hard to interpret, which is further highlighted by the voltage response in the time domain while the spectra were recorded.

Figure 6. Impedance spectra (top) and associated voltage response in the time domain (bottom) obtained by sinusoidal perturbation (left) and by PRBS perturbation (right).

In order to better visualise the impact of the test conditions on the stack impedance, the spectra that belonged to the same series have been averaged in Figure 7. Obviously better quality spectra are obtained now, where it can be seen that increased fuel utilization causes a considerable increase of the low frequency feature. A shift towards lower frequency was not observed for the considered dataset. In addition, a slight increase in Ohmic resistance can be seen in the plots at 1030 W, but this is not the case at 570 W.

Figure 7. Averaged Nyquist plots (left) and Bode plots (right) obtained at 1030 W (top) and 570 W (middle) for sinusoidal perturbation, and at 570 W (bottom) for PRBS perturbation.

In Figure 8, the DRT graphs are shown for the sinusoidal impedance spectra displayed in Figure 7, obtained after Tikhonov regularization with inductance correction within the regularization problem [25], a method that worked well for datasets obtained on short stacks in an earlier phase of the project (results not reported here). Generally good reproducibility can be observed for frequencies above 1 kHz. At lower frequencies, the results are less clear. This implies that the method requires further improvement, for which additional good quality datasets under well defined conditions that are obtained in the system under investigation are needed.

Figure 8. Sinusoidal impedance spectra deconvoluted by DRT at 1030 W (left) and 570 W (right)

3.4 Fault detection and isolation results

The FDI algorithm includes a design part that is constructed prior to the online measurements, and an application part that compares the actual status with the design part. Important steps in the offline part were parameter extractions from representative tests done under controlled conditions (experimental data obtained by EPFL, DTU and CEA, results not reported here) by means of a proprietary ECM deconvolution algorithm [31], the subsequent determination of threshold levels of these parameters, and the final construction of the fault signature matrix (FSM). For the online monitoring, the same algorithm for parameter extraction is used, the values of which are compared with the FSM, and ultimately leading to fault isolation and state of health assessment.

As an example, Figure 9 shows the extracted low frequency resistances for the sinusoidal impedance measurements performed at 1030W power. It can be seen that the FDI algorithm detects fuel starvation when the fuel utilization exceeds 70%, with 71% accuracy at 70% fuel utilization, and 91% at 72% fuel utilization. Similar scores were obtained at 570 W power and 72% fuel utilization.

Figure 9. Gas conversion impedance (Ohm.cm²) at 1030 W extracted by means of the ECM routine (top) as a function of fuel utilization that ranged between 62 and 72%, and subsequent output examples of the FDI algorithm shown on the GUI (Graphical User Interface), which is the actual output of the board running real time with the stack, distinguishing normal operation (green), faulty operation (red) and unclear faulty operation (yellow) while driving the system towards fuel starvation.

4. Conclusions

Important steps towards SoH monitoring of a commercial SOFC system by means of total harmonics distortion and impedance spectroscopy have been made. The results show that the developed hardware and diagnostic routines for stack perturbation and fault detection accurately detect fuel starvation. An important finding was that the analysed process signals contained noise that is likely caused by the system control. The noise can be suppressed by increasing the perturbation, which was demonstrated for THDA, or by signal averaging, which was demonstrated for impedance spectroscopy by means of sinusoidal perturbation and PRBS perturbation. In addition, it was shown that the developed routine to deconvolute impedance spectra by DRT, which was previously successfully validated for short stacks, requires further improvement to be used in the commercial system.

It was further shown that the FDI algorithm detects fuel starvation on the system when the fuel utilization exceeds 70%, with 71% accuracy at 70% fuel utilization, and 91% at 72% fuel utilization.

It is expected that the findings provide a good basis for further maturing the SoH monitoring approach for other faults, where deeper implementation in the control and fault mitigation strategy can be considered.

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